

Analysis of Law Relating to Arbitration Agreement in India

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Abstract:

Arbitration agreement is the foundation of arbitration process and without having the agreement parties to the dispute cannot resort to the arbitration mechanism. Arbitration process presupposes the arbitration agreement. It is general practice of the parties to incorporate an arbitration agreement or arbitration clause in the business contract. The arbitration agreement is the mechanism to resolve disputes which may arise in future course of time. As and when the parties to the business contract dispute on certain issue they refer the arbitration agreement to resolve the dispute. However, it is not mandatory to incorporate the arbitration agreement on the date of executing the business agreement. The arbitration agreement should be clear to understand and no room should be left to vagueness. The drafting of the arbitration agreement requires no legal qualifications but warrants legal knowledge as it involves the basic knowledge of the law of contract. It is suggested that the parties to the dispute or to the business contract to have the clauses and the arbitration agreement vetted by the person having legal knowledge so that the parties can mitigate the risk of losing the choice of having an alternative dispute resolution mechanism.

Introduction:

Arbitration agreement is the foundation of arbitration process and without having the agreement parties to the dispute cannot resort to the arbitration mechanism. Arbitration process presupposes the arbitration agreement. It is general practice of the parties to incorporate an arbitration agreement or arbitration clause in the business contract. The arbitration agreement is the mechanism to resolve disputes which may arise in future course of time. As and when the parties to the business contract dispute on certain issue they refer the arbitration agreement to resolve the dispute. However, it is not mandatory to incorporate the arbitration agreement on the date of executing the business agreement. It is the choice of the parties either to incorporate it from the day of business agreement or as and when the dispute arises. This means, the parties can resort

to arbitration mechanism by entering into a fresh arbitration agreement. Thus, notwithstanding the time when the arbitration agreement is incorporated in the business agreement, it is a precondition to resort to the arbitration mechanism to resolve disputes.

The drafting of arbitration agreement assumes paramount importance because it confers rights and obligations upon the parties. Vague language and loose terms give rise to contradictions and confusions which again become a separate dispute. To avoid such vagueness and to ensure the smooth process of dispute resolution, it requires skill of drafting the arbitration agreement. Many times, the courts have pointed at the poor drafting of the arbitration agreements. The courts have declared such agreements as invalid and made certain guidelines as to what and how the agreement should be drafted in the business contract. In India, the arbitration agreement is defined under Section 7 of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996. The researcher tries to find what and what not is arbitration agreement. The researcher also tries to find out whether it requires legal knowledge to draft the arbitration agreement.

Materials and methods:

The research materials include secondary and primary sources. The secondary materials explain the law. They include journals, annotations, and treatises. The primary sources are the Acts and the cases decided by the courts in India.

Data Analysis:

Researcher collected the data of cases and the Acts relevant to the arbitration agreement and analyzed the data in the following paragraphs. Section 7 of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996 reads arbitration agreement.—*In this Part, “arbitration agreement” means an agreement by the parties to submit to arbitration all or certain disputes which have arisen or which may arise between them in respect of a defined legal relationship, whether contractual or not. An arbitration agreement may be in the form of an arbitration clause in a contract or in the form of a separate agreement. An arbitration agreement shall be in writing. An arbitration agreement is in writing if it is contained in—a document signed by the parties; an exchange of letters, telex, telegrams or other means of telecommunication [including communication through electronic*

means]¹ which provide a record of the agreement; or an exchange of statements of claim and defence in which the existence of the agreement is alleged by one party and not denied by the other. The reference in a contract to a document containing an arbitration clause constitutes an arbitration agreement if the contract is in writing and the reference is such as to make that arbitration clause part of the contract.²

The arbitration agreement under this section is based on Article 7 of UNCITRAL Model Law. The elements as defined under section 2(1)(b) read with section 7 are: Valid and binding agreement between the parties. Agreement may be in the form of a clause or in the form of a separate agreement. Agreement must be in writing. The parties' intention to refer the present or future disputes to arbitration. Defined legal relationship whether contractual or not. The arbitration agreement is the edifice of the arbitration mechanism. Let us understand the text of definition given under section 7 of the Act. Section 7(1) says it is an agreement to submit to arbitration all or certain disputes which have arisen or which may arise. This means the parties may have differed on many issues or may have alleged against each other with many disputes and when the alleging party wishes to resort to arbitration may not necessarily to refer all the disputes but it is party's prerogative to refer all or certain disputes. For instance, X may have 4 number of disputes against Y and X may refer to arbitration either all 4 or any of the 4 disputes.

In the same sub-section, the text extends to the disputes arising in respect of defined relationship whether contractual or not. This means the non-contractual matters can also be referred if they are covered within the defined legal relationship. For instance, certain disputes involve third parties touching the contractual matter, infringement of intellectual property rights like copyright, trademark, patents, etc. claims arising out of tort may not be out of a defined legal relationship though they give rise to a legal claim and a remedy.³ Negotiating a bargain does not form an arbitration agreement. Mere use of the word 'arbitration' or 'arbitrator' in a clause will not make it an arbitration agreement, if it requires or contemplates a further or fresh consent of the

¹ Ins. by Act 3 of 2016, s. 3 (w. e. f. 23-10-2015).

² Section 7 of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996.

³ Ghewarchand Rampuriya V. Shiva Jute Bailing Ltd., AIR 1950 Cal 568.

parties for reference to arbitration.⁴ For example, use of words such as "parties can, if they so desire, refer their disputes to arbitration" or "in the event of any dispute, the parties may also agree to refer the same to arbitration" or "if any disputes arise between the parties, they should consider settlement by arbitration" in a clause relating to settlement of disputes, indicate that the clause is not intended to be an arbitration agreement.

The essentials of a valid arbitration agreement was explained in K.K. Modi's case.⁵ It was held in this case that a valid arbitration agreement – must contemplate that the decision of the tribunal will be binding on the parties to the agreement; must contemplate that substantive rights of parties will be determined by the agreed tribunal; must contemplate that the tribunal will make a decision upon a dispute which is already formulated at the time when a reference is made to the tribunal; jurisdiction of the tribunal to decide the rights of parties must be derived either from the consent of the parties or from an order of the Court or from a statute, the terms of which make it clear that the process is to be an arbitration; the tribunal will determine the rights of the parties in an impartial and judicial manner with the tribunal owing an equal obligation of fairness towards both sides; and agreement of the parties to refer their disputes to the decision of the tribunal must be intended to be enforceable in law.

Even where only certain correspondences indicated a reference to the contract containing arbitration clause for opening the letter of credit addressed to the bank, and no correspondence between the parties disagreed with terms of the contract or arbitration clause, it was a valid arbitration agreement.⁶ The intention of the parties matters a lot and it is the most significant element to ascertain the existence of arbitration agreement.⁷

Doctrine of Severability in respect of Arbitration Clause:

As per this doctrine, the invalid terms of the arbitration agreement can be ignored and the valid terms could be enforced. *"One of the clauses related to arbitration which was in various*

⁴ Jagdish Chander vs Ramesh Chander & Ors (2007) 5 SCC 719

⁵ K. K. Modi v. K. N. Modi, (1998) 3 SCC 573

⁶ Smitha Conductors v. Euro Alloys Ltd., (2001) 7 SCC 728

⁷ Shakti Bhog Foods Ltd. v. Kola Shipping Ltd., (2009) 2 SCC 134

parts. The first part mandated that, if there is a dispute between the parties, it shall be referred to and finally resolved by arbitration. It clarifies that the rules of UNCITRAL would apply to such arbitration. It then directs that the arbitration shall be held in Delhi and will be in English language. It stipulates that the costs of arbitration shall be shared by the parties equally. The offending and objectionable part, no doubt, expressly makes the arbitrator's determination 'final and binding between the parties' and declares that the parties have waived the rights of appeal or objection 'in any jurisdiction'. The said objectionable part however is clearly severable as it is independent of the dispute being referred to and resolved by an arbitrator. Hence, even in the absence of any other clause, the part as to referring the dispute to arbitrator can be given effect to and enforced. By implementing that part, it cannot be said that the Court is doing something which is not contemplated by the parties or by 'interpretative process', the Court is re-writing the contract which is in the nature of 'novatio'. The intention of the parties is explicitly clear and they have agreed that the dispute, if any, would be referred to an arbitrator. To that extent, therefore, the agreement is legal, lawful and the offending part as to the finality and restraint in approaching a Court of law can be separated and severed by using a blue pencil".⁸

It establishes that the arbitration agreement is separate from the contract and exists individually without regard to the invalidity of the contract. The effect is that the validity of the main contract, if challenged, can be adjudicated upon such arbitration clause. Termination of contract does not amount to termination of arbitration clause.

Effect of Frustration of Contract on Arbitration Agreement:

Let us understand the law on frustration in a contract. Section 56 of the Indian Contract Act 1872 provides that "*an agreement to do an act impossible in itself is void. —An agreement to do an act impossible in itself is void.*" *Contract to do act afterwards becoming impossible or unlawful.—A contract to do an act which, after the contract is made, becomes impossible, or, by reason of some event which the promisor could not prevent, unlawful, becomes void when the act becomes impossible or unlawful. Compensation for loss through non-performance of act known to*

⁸ Shin Satellite Public Co. Ltd. v Jain Studios Ltd. (2006) 2SCC 628, 637.

be impossible or unlawful.—Where one person has promised to do something which he knew, or, with reasonable diligence, might have known, and which the promisee did not know, to be impossible or unlawful, such promisor must make compensation to such promisee for any loss which such promisee sustains through the non-performance of the promise."

The effect of frustration of contract is irrelevant to the arbitration agreement. The arbitration clause would still prevail. This position is statutorily recognized under section 16(1) of the Act which makes it clear that while considering any objection with respect to the existence or validity of the arbitration agreement, an arbitration clause which forms a part of the contract has to be treated as an agreement independent of the other terms of the contract and a decision that the contract is null and void shall not entail ipso jure the invalidity of the arbitration clause.

Arbitration agreement and Expert Opinion:

The expert opinion is not an award and hence any reference for expert's determination on any issue is not reference of dispute for adjudication and it cannot be termed as arbitration agreement unless otherwise specifically provided in the contract.

Disputes referable to arbitration:

All disputes arising out of defined relationship whether contractual or not can be referred to arbitration however subject to limitations of section 2 (3) of the Act of 1996. As per this provision, the following disputes cannot be subjected to arbitration: Insolvency matters, matrimonial causes, testamentary matters, etc. According to the section 7 of the Act non contractual disputes can also be referred to arbitration only when they are covered under the category of defined legal relationship. All tortious acts are under the category of defined legal relationships.

SCOTT V AVERY CLAUSE IN INDIA

It is a clause in a contract where parties agree to submit any disputes between them to arbitration before deciding to pursue remedies in a court of law. Under Arbitration and Conciliation Act 1996, an arbitration agreement which ousts the jurisdiction of courts would be void. But the

parties can stipulate that the award of the arbitrator shall be a condition precedent to the maintainability of any suit. In such cases the award becomes prerequisite. The validity of Scott v Avery clause was dealt by the Supreme Court in India in Vulcan Insurance Co. Ltd vs Maharaj Singh & Another, 1976 AIR 287. *“A clause like the one in the Scott v Avery bars any action or suit if commenced for determination of a dispute covered by an arbitration clause. But if on the other hand, a dispute cropped up at the very outset which cannot be referred to arbitration as being not covered by the clause, then the Scott v Avery clause is rendered inoperative and cannot be pleaded as a bar to the maintainability of the legal action or suit for determination of the dispute which was outside the arbitration clause”.*⁹

Conclusion:

The study and analysis of the above data and cases establishes that the arbitration agreement should have the true intention of the parties and it should be in writing. The arbitration agreement should be clear to understand and no room should be left to vagueness. The drafting of the arbitration agreement requires no legal qualifications but warrants legal knowledge as it involves the basic knowledge of the law of contract. It is suggested that the parties to the dispute or to the business contract to have the clauses and the arbitration agreement vetted by the person having legal knowledge so that the parties can mitigate the risk of losing the choice of having an alternative dispute resolution mechanism.

⁹ *Manohar Reddy & Bros. V/s Maharashtra Krishna Valley Development Corporation*, (2009) 2 SCC 494.